
NATIONAL CULTURAL CENTERS ARE A MIRROR OF SOLIDARITY

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada mustaqillik yillarida mamlakatimizda milliy-madaniy markazlarning tashkil etilishining maqsad va vazifalari, milliy-madaniy markazlarnig faoliyatini rivojlantirish borasida yurtboshimiz rahnamoligida olib borilayotgan ishlarning mazmun-mohiyati yoritib berilgan.

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны цели и задачи создания национально-культурных центров в нашей стране в годы независимости, суть работы, проводимой под руководством президента нашей страны по развитию деятельности национально-культурных центров.

Abstract: This article describes the goals and tasks of the establishment of national cultural centers in our country during the years of independence, the essence of the work carried out under the leadership of our country's president to develop the activities of national cultural centers.

Kalit so‘zlar: Milliy-madaniy markazlar, millatlararo totuvlik, dinlararo bag’rikenglik, demografik jarayonlar

Ключевые слова: Национально-культурные центры, межнациональное согласие, межрелигиозная толерантность, демографические процессы

Key words: National-cultural centers, interethnic harmony, interreligious tolerance, demographic processes.

National-cultural centers are community organizations that serve to meet the national cultural needs of a specific ethnic group residing in Uzbekistan.

The national-cultural center operates in accordance with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and public organizations, as well as based on its own regulations.

National-cultural centers bring together Uzbekistan citizens who are interested in learning, preserving, and developing the national culture, language, customs, traditions, and cuisine unique to a specific ethnic group. They are established in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On Non-Governmental and Non-Profit Organizations' (April 14, 1999).

The relevant judicial authorities (Ministry of Justice or regional and city justice departments) register national-cultural centers. They operate directly or through their branches within the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The initial national-cultural centers were established by Koreans, Kazakhs, Jews, and Armenians in the republics and regions in 1989. The genuine development and organization of these centers began after Uzbekistan gained independence. Wide opportunities were created for them to operate effectively in connection with the independence of Uzbekistan.

As a result, the number of national-cultural centers has steadily increased over the years. If there were only 10 national-cultural centers in 1992, their number reached 72 in 1995, and by 2003, it had grown to 135. They include republic-level cultural centers as well as regional, city, and district cultural centers.

Since the early days of independence, a state policy has been pursued aimed at fostering interethnic harmony and tolerance. This policy aims to create favorable conditions for various ethnic groups to live freely and independently in Uzbekistan. This can be seen in the establishment of the Republic International Cultural Center by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 13, 1992. Society is further strengthened by promoting healthy lifestyles, interethnic harmony, mutual respect, and creating an environment of religious tolerance. Additionally, efforts are made to preserve and pass on the ancient customs and traditions of our multi-ethnic people, instilling in the younger generation a deep love for their homeland, loyalty to independence, and a sense of devotion to the motherland. In the Fergana Valley region, activities of national-cultural centers are being carried out to coordinate and further develop their activities in accordance with these goals, which have begun to yield positive results.

In particular, considering the significant demand for community representation in Andijan province, 5 national cultural centers have been established, specifically for Uyghur, Korean, Armenian, Kyrgyz, and Russian communities, taking into account the need to address national needs. These centers play an important role in strengthening friendship, harmony, peace, and tolerance in our society. One of these national-cultural centers is the Uyghur Cultural Center, which was one of the first national-cultural centers established in Uzbekistan in 1989 and operates in the province.

One of the important directions of the activity of national-cultural centers in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to ensure the active participation of various ethnic groups living in the republic in the social, cultural, and educational life of the country. Additionally, establishing and developing friendly, cooperative, cultural, and educational relations with diaspora organizations and their historical homelands in foreign countries, as well as promoting friendship and cooperation, enhancing mutual

understanding and interethnic harmony among citizens in our country through cooperation with Republic International Cultural Center, relevant ministries, agencies, state and public organizations, and creative associations, is considered the main tasks of the center in contributing to the unity and interethnic harmony of citizens in our country.

According to the regulations, centers carry out the following types of activities to achieve the specified goals and tasks: organizing study groups and Saturday schools for learning music and theater studios, mother tongue, history, writing, literature, oral folklore, theater and painting art, national customs and craftsmanship, national sports and games in accordance with applicable legislation; conducting seminars, conferences, roundtable discussions, festivals, and meetings to study and promote national culture, national language, national art forms, and national customs; and establishing cultural and artistic communities. The Republic International Cultural Center, established by the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 13, 1992, coordinates the activities of national-cultural centers.

In the coming years, comprehensive measures will be implemented in our country to enhance the spiritual and cultural level of our people, strengthen the material-technical base of cultural and art institutions, and support professionals in the field.

In particular, to support Uzbekistan's creators, initiatives such as the "Ilkhom" Community Foundation, the Development Fund for Culture and Arts under the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Association of Uzbekistan Composers and Conductors, the Uzbekistan State Philharmonic, and the Fergana Regional Branch of the Uzbekistan State Institute of Arts and Culture have been established.

A system has been created to collect and develop unique examples and traditions of Uzbek classical and folk art. The Uzbek National Maqom Art Center and Museum were established. The organization of the International Maqom Art Forum and the International Bakhshi Art Festival every two years has been a significant practical step in increasing the influence of our unique heritage on a global scale.

Our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev finds his way into each of our hearts, inspires and encourages us. For me, every inch of this land is precious, not a single drop of water is insignificant. The Uzbek people say, 'You, me, all of us who have lived through this era are dear.'

As the population continues to grow in accordance with economic and social laws, demographic processes also develop in relation to specific production methods and attitudes towards production. The population is a complex social and natural development product, influenced by various factors. From this perspective, it closely

analyzes the subjects of economics, sociology, geography, medicine, and history, benefiting from their achievements and providing important information to them at the same time. Economic and social development plays a significant role in shaping demographic processes. Improving living standards, improving the quality of medical services positively affect demographic processes, leading to an increase in the population. Wars, various diseases, economic crises, migration, and other factors have a negative impact on demographic processes according to their characteristics.

Demographic processes refer to events related to changes in generations in people's lives.

Demographic processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan during the years of independence differ from previous periods in their uniqueness. The increase in the average life expectancy of the population in the last twenty years from 67 to 73.8 years indicates many positive aspects. Specifically, the life expectancy of women has reached 76.2 years, while for men it is 71.4 years. Uzbekistan's transition to the path of independent development marked the beginning of a new phase in its demographic history. New demographic changes have emerged as a result of changes in social, economic, and political conditions shaping market relations in the country. This, in turn, has had its impact on the multicultural relations of our republic, which is home to many ethnicities.

Instead of summarizing, it is worth emphasizing that as a result of the measures being taken to strengthen the environment based on positive and mutual respect in the field of interethnic harmony and religious tolerance in our country, a new model of interethnic and interreligious relations has been created. This model is based on constructive dialogue and equal rights for all citizens under the law, fostering interaction between various ethnic and religious representatives. In this context, the comprehensive reforms implemented in recent years in Uzbekistan in the field of interethnic relations and religion have contributed to the formation of a system that combines innovative approaches and strategic goals in these areas.

The success of this system is aimed at creating a conducive environment for maintaining peace, ensuring the security of citizens, and promoting sustainable development in our country. Indeed, the main goal of the modern state is to ensure effective protection of social cohesion, stability, and human rights and freedoms in society. In this regard, our fundamental law - the Constitution - is not only a high-level political and legal document defining the progress of society and the state but also a crucial foundation guaranteeing the appropriate living conditions of every citizen residing in our country.

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